

IN VIVO TESTING OF A PHOSPHATE GLASS FIBRE / PLA COMPOSITE USING A RABBIT TIBIA MODEL

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1 General Introduction

Rigid internal fixation with metal plates is a well-established treatment in modern fracture management enabling early mobilisation through stabilisation of the fracture site. However, the relatively stiff nature of these implants can affect the normal strain environment of the underlying bone, leading to profound structural changes that progress with the duration of implantation [1,2]. These “stress shielding” changes include reduced cortical thickness and density and increased porosity with a consequent risk of re-fracture if the plate is removed. Metal plates may also act as permanent sites of infection and interfere with neighbouring nerves and tendons as well as with overlying soft tissues. Plate removal can be necessary for these reasons.

These disadvantages have acted as an impetus for the development of biodegradable plates with transitional mechanical properties and an overall reduced stiffness, allowing for greater load sharing with the host bone and adaptation to the evolving mechanics of the bone as it heals. These plates would not require removal and as they degraded, would transfer increasing loads to the host bone progressively. Such an implant avoids the risks of second surgery, including additional scarring, tissue damage and potential infection. However, the inferior mechanical properties of synthetic polymers that are used currently (such as polylactic acid (PLA), polyglycolic acid (PGA) and polycaprolactone (PCL)) and reported complications of soft tissue inflammatory reactions caused by their degradation behaviour have restricted progress [3].

Phosphate glass fibre (PGF) reinforced PLA composites are a unique class of resorbable synthetic materials with relatively high stiffness (similar to conventional E-glass composites). They have been

shown to have initial mechanical properties surpassing that of cortical bone, enabling use in load bearing applications while retaining the ability to degrade in vivo [4]. Degradation characteristics can be tailored by modifying the composite design and fibre chemistry. The authors have established a wide range of different glass formulations with different degradation rates [5-9] and in vitro studies have demonstrated satisfactory biocompatibility with human cell lines [7-9]. Composites of these materials have also shown good in vitro behaviour [10-12].

The aim of the current study was to determine the in vivo degradation characteristics of a novel resorbable PGF-PLA composite plate in an animal model and the adaptive bone response at the site of implantation. The chosen animal model was the intact tibiae of New Zealand White rabbits. The intact bone was chosen so that the adaptive response of the bone could be studied without the confounding influence of fracture biology.

Prior to the in vivo study, extensive development and characterisation of the materials and device were undertaken. This included investigation of the effects of fibre orientation and composite layup on mechanical properties and implant preparation (moulding, cutting and drilling operations) as well as the effects of sterilisation [13]. The design of the implant was based on a standard metal plate for small bone fixation.

2 Materials and Methods

Phosphate glass of the formulation 40P₂O₅ - 16CaO - 24MgO - 16Na₂O - 4Fe₂O₃ (in mol%) was produced by fusing sodium dihydrogen phosphate (NaH₂PO₄), calcium hydrogen phosphate (CaHPO₄), magnesium hydrogen phosphate trihydrate

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(MgHPO₄·3H₂O) and iron(III)phosphate dihydrate (FePO₄·2H₂O) salts in appropriate quantities in a 5%Au/95%Pt crucible at 1100 °C for 90 minutes. The glass was cast onto a room temperature stainless steel plate and allowed to cool.

This glass was then processed into fibres using an in-house fibre manufacturing facility [4]. The fibres were wound onto a traversing drum to obtain unidirectionally aligned (UD) fibres, which were bound together using a sprayed solution of PLA in chloroform. The UD pre-preg sheets were trimmed to fit a mould of 110mm×125mm. Non-woven random aligned fibre mats (RM) were produced using chopped fibres (10mm length), via an airlay process that has been described previously [11].

The grade of PLA that was used to produce the composites was PURASORB®PLDL 8038; a non-crystallising medical grade that is a blend of 80% L-lactide with 20% DL-lactide, with an intrinsic viscosity of 3.8 dl/g. Sheets of this material were prepared for inclusion in the composite by hot pressing at 210°C and 3 bar for 10 minutes.

Composites were produced by stacking UD and RM fibre mats sandwiched between PLA sheets, which were then hot pressed at 210°C and 38 bar. The layup was 2 layers of RM mats top and bottom (included to prevent splitting during drilling and fixation to the bone with screws), with additional UD mats to achieve a desired volume fraction of approximately 40% fibre. The process is illustrated in figure 1.

Fig. 1. Method of producing composites. (a) PLA-bound unidirectional fibre mat produced directly from fibre manufacturing rig. (b) PLA bound random fibre mat produced via airlaying. (c) PLA

polymer sheets produced by hot pressing. (d) Film stacking process to produce composite.

Implant plates were produced according to the dimensions in Fig. 2. They were cut with a fine toothed band saw and finished to size and shape using multiple grades of sandpaper.

Fig. 2. Schematic of the implant plate dimensions, showing location of screw holes (dimensions in mm) (top). Example of final composite piece (bottom).

Holes were cut in the specimens by clamping them in a steel jig (Fig. 3.) before cutting the holes with a high speed drill so as to prevent any delamination.

Fig. 3. Drilling jig for composites. The composite is placed in the slot in the upper section and then clamped in place under the plate shown at the bottom of the image. Alignment is provided by a rod through the large hole on the left of the jig.

After they were prepared, the composites were then sterilised by using gamma radiation, with a dose of approximately 36 Grays, via a commercial process.

Control plates were used that were made out of surgical grade stainless steel of the same dimensions, treated with an equivalent sterilisation procedure.

Two sets of twenty-five New Zealand White rabbits underwent surgical application of either the composite or metal plate to the anteromedial aspect of the intact right tibia using conventional stainless steel screws (Fig. 4.). A stainless steel alignment jig and rods were used to ensure good fixation in all cases. The rabbits were divided into equal groups corresponding to the time points from surgery to sacrifice – 2, 6, 12, 26 and 52 weeks. Intra-cardiac perfusion of formalin was applied under terminal anaesthesia to enable rapid fixation for histology outcomes. The influence of implantation duration on plate degradation and bone and soft tissue reaction were assessed. Radiographs of both tibiae were taken immediately after surgery and at sacrifice to assess qualitative changes in the bone.

Fig. 4. Radiograph showing the placement of the implants on the rabbit tibia.

Retrieved tibiae from three of the five rabbits at each time point were subjected to flexural testing in an Instron testing machine to determine the mechanical characteristics of the combined bone-plate construct

with respect to the opposite unplate control tibia. All tibiae were loaded to failure, and the ultimate load to failure and flexural stiffness were obtained. Three point bend flexural tests were conducted with a span of 40 mm and a cross-head speed of 5 mm/min, with the samples orientated as shown in figure 5.

Fig. 5. Radiograph demonstrating the orientation of the bone/plate construct during mechanical testing

Cortical thickness was analysed quantitatively using Nano Computed Tomography (nanoCT) imaging (composite only) and Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) of resin embedded axial slices of the bone-plate construct. The bone/composite constructs were sectioned for SEM by using a diamond saw and were subsequently carbon coated and imaged at an accelerating voltage of 20 kV using SE (Secondary electron) mode.

The remaining retrieved tibiae were used for histological studies, using both as removed and decalcified specimens. Histological staining techniques were used to evaluate inflammation of the soft tissues surrounding the implant.

3 Results and Discussion

There was no evidence of macroscopic inflammation at any time point of retrieval for the composite plates, with no radiographic evidence of osteolysis. One incidence of tissue swelling occurred in the metal specimens but showed no signs of infection. Capsule formation was apparent in all the specimens, which increased over the course of the implantation up to 52 weeks. Examples of the capsules are shown in Fig. 6. Macroscopic integrity of the plates was maintained for the 52 week period.

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Fig. 6. Soft tissue encapsulation of the plates observed after retrieval at two weeks (top) and at 52 weeks (bottom)

Radiographic imaging during the course of the study showed evidence of the reducing thickness of the composite plate, while the thickness of the bone cortex beneath the plate remained relatively unchanged. With the metal plate, there is a clear reduction in the thickness of the bone cortex (see Figs. 7a, 7b and 8.). This is strong evidence to support the effect of different stiffness materials when attached to a bone surface. Bone is known to remodel when placed under stress (or lack of) [1,2] and here the relatively high stiffness steel is providing a ‘stress bridge’ between the sets of screws. This results in the unloaded central portion of the bone remodeling and weakening, which can be a cause of re-fracture should the plate be removed.

Fig.7a. Radiographs of retrieved tibiae with composite specimens

Left to right: 2 weeks, 6 weeks, 12 weeks, 24 weeks, 52 weeks.

Fig.7a. Radiographs of retrieved tibiae with metal specimens

Left to right: 2 weeks, 6 weeks, 12 weeks, 24 weeks

Fig. 8. Radiographs at 26 weeks revealed a thinning of the cortex under the metal plate (arrow in lower image) but not the composite plate (upper image).

Bone formation was noted at the periphery of the plate after 2 weeks for both composite and metal plates. Bone thickening is also noticeable around the screws. A more in depth analysis of the bone formation around the plate was performed by using both SEM and nanoCT analysis. The bones were sectioned at common sites along the length of the bone to provide ease of comparison, as shown in Fig. 8. below.

Fig. 8. Photograph illustrating the sections taken through the bone, to assess the response of the bone in different areas of interest.

Analysis of the cut sections demonstrated the growth and development of new bone around the plates during implantation. Fig. 9. shows SEM and Fig. 10 shows nanoCT of the composite specimen after 2 weeks of implantation. New, highly porous bone can be seen growing around the edges of the plate, as well as both under the plate and on the opposite cortex. This is believed to be at least in part a reaction to the 'insult' of screw insertion. Such a reaction does not occur in the control tibia.

Fig. 9. SEM of composite specimen at 2 weeks. New, highly porous bone is seen clearly growing up the edges of the specimen as well as both faces of the cortex.

Fig. 10. nanoCT of the 2 week composite specimen, showing bone growth at the edges of the plate and in the cortices (left). The opposite control bone does not show any new growth (right)

This new bone growth becomes dense mature bone by the 6 week time point (Fig. 11.). However, at subsequent time points this becomes porous again (Fig. 12.), to a greater or less extent, before becoming fully dense at 52 weeks.

Fig. 11. The composite specimen at 6 weeks. The new bone growth has now become dense, mature bone.

Fig. 12. The newly formed dense bone starts to increase in porosity, indicating remodeling.

This process can be seen quite clearly in the nanoCT in Fig. 13. where it is apparent also that the cortex below the composite has in fact reduced in thickness slightly, although the amount of bone buttressing around the composite is quite significant. These changes in the bone suggest that even with a relatively low stiffness material like the composite,

Fig. 13. nanoCT images of the composite specimen at different time points. (a) 6 weeks (b) 12 weeks (c) 26 weeks (d) 52 weeks. Refer to Fig. 10. for the 2 week specimen. The changes in bone structure are quite apparent.

the change in stress distribution is sufficient to cause quite drastic changes in the bone.

Similar image analysis studies are underway with the metal plated specimens, although the metal causes interference with nanoCT, which creates difficulties with the imaging. Based on the radiography and since the metal plate is stiffer and will not reduce in stiffness during the course of the study, it is expected that a similar or more extreme result will be observed.

In contrast to the apparent changes in the morphology of the bones during the course of the study, the mechanical properties remain remarkably consistent. With the composite plates specimens, both the load to failure and flexural stiffness of the bone/plate constructs remain fairly constant (Fig.14.). This consistency in properties suggests that an overall property is maintained by the bone biology, to fit the demand of the overall environment.

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The changes in the bone porosity indicate the adjustments that occur in the bone to keep this 'status quo'. In vitro analysis of the composite plate suggests a gradual loss of stiffness over the period. This could account for the porosity during the middle stages of the study and a final, dense bone by the 52 week period, by which time the composite stiffness is much less than it was initially. Such a change is desirable and could be matched more efficiently to the bone biology. However, it should be borne in mind that the healing rates of rabbits are considerably faster than those of humans, such that a more gradual change in stiffness may be desirable.

Fig. 14. Ultimate load (top) and flexural stiffness (bottom) of composite plated tibiae in comparison to control tibiae up to 52 weeks, showing relatively consistent properties

The reason for the unusual peak in properties of the control tibia at 26 weeks is unclear. It may be related to the age of the rabbit, since they would reach maturity during the course of the study. The effect occurs to some degree in the metal plated specimens as well (see Fig. 15) and so it is likely to be related to the rabbit, rather than the plate, but bears further consideration.

Fig. 15. Ultimate load (top) and flexural stiffness (bottom) of metal plated tibiae in comparison to control tibiae up to 26 weeks.

The metal plated bones show considerably greater properties, both for load and stiffness, as would be expected. However, the metal plated specimens also

show a difference in profile. The properties increase from 2 weeks to 6 weeks and then begin to drop by 26 weeks. This may reflect an increasing porosity and reduction in cortical thickness at later time points. This is indeed indicated by the radiography (Figs. 7a and 8.), which should be corroborated by SEM data. Despite the loss, the flexural biomechanical properties of the bone-plate construct remained higher than the control up to 26 weeks. 52 week mechanical data and SEM images for the metal plates are expected to be available soon.

Conclusions

The global properties of the composite plate-bone construct were consistent for the period of the study, despite changes in the bone density over the period. The metal-bone construct global properties reached a peak before decreasing, with apparent loss of cortical thickness underneath the plate. In both cases the plated bones maintained properties that were higher than the control bone.

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